

TOWARDS AN INTEGRATED PROCESSING MODEL FOR A CO-MINGLED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

T. A. Cain, M. D. Wakeman, R. Brooks, A. C. Long and C. D. Rudd

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Nottingham, UK.

SUMMARY: This paper describes work which has been undertaken in order to model the three major processes which occur during the processing of a co-mingled thermoplastic composite, namely material deformation, consolidation and heat transfer. Material deformation has been modelled using a kinematic fabric draping model which predicts fibre orientation, and which may be used to estimate variations in local component thickness. The consolidation model, which predicts developed moulding pressure, is a 1-D formulation based on fibre bed compaction and matrix flow in fibre bundles. Heat transfer during processing is simulated via a 1-D through-thickness formulation which predicts the temperature distribution within the laminate. This model uses simple convective and conductive boundary terms so that the temperature distribution within the laminate may be determined at any instant from the end of pre-heat, up to the completion of moulding. The paper concludes with a discussion on the integration of these models, and the utility of the resulting processing model in component and process design.

KEYWORDS: modelling, co-mingled, thermoplastic, consolidation, fabric deformation, heat transfer

INTRODUCTION

Co-mingled fabrics allow production of parts containing aligned glass fibres at higher volume fractions using lower moulding pressures than are attainable using flow moulded materials. This makes them particularly attractive to the automotive industry with the potential to permit cost and weight benefits over established material systems. Several manufacturing routes exist for processing of co-mingled materials including press moulding, vacuum bagging and autoclave moulding. In order to produce high quality laminates using any of these processes it is important to have an understanding of the effect of the processing parameters upon the finished laminate. Through the development and integration of models for the deformation, consolidation and cooling of a co-mingled thermoplastic laminate, the component design and process optimisation can be integrated with a reduced need for experimentation and prototyping.

DEFORMATION

Several workers have investigated the application of large deformation shell finite-element theories to the prediction of draped fabric forms [1, 2]. Good results may be obtained via this route, but the method can appear computationally expensive in comparison to the kinematic fabric deformation models which others have used for drape simulation, notably Long [3] and Van West [4].

The fabric deformation simulation in this work is based on kinematic drape model developed at Nottingham. This model assumes that the fabric drapes over a surface via in-plane fabric shearing only.

In order to generate a unique solution for the draped configuration, one fibre path in each of the warp and the weft directions must be constrained. Fig. 1 shows the predicted fibre configuration when a fabric is draped over a thick disc mounted on a flat plate. In this example, symmetry has been used to reduce the scale of the modelling problem, and the constrained fibre paths are co-incident with the planes of symmetry.

Fig. 1: Draped fabric configuration—2 views

CONSOLIDATION

Previous investigators, notably Klinkmuller [5], Ye [6] and Van West [7], have studied the impregnation and consolidation mechanisms occurring during the isothermal compaction of co-mingled materials. Van West developed a 1-D consolidation model for co-mingled materials based on a worst-state case of fibre interspersion, with the glass and matrix material located in two adjacent, but completely separate regions. Staged compaction of a co-mingled fabric has been used to obtain micrographs of the fibre dispersion and matrix impregnation at states of consolidation ranging from unconsolidated to completely consolidated [8]. Observations from these micrographs suggest a modification to the Van West Model which allows improved simulation of the fibre dispersions for the material under study. In addition,

an investigation into the effect of in-plane shear on fabric compaction has been undertaken in order to allow further modification to the consolidation model.

Experimental Details

Materials

A balanced twill weave fabric of superficial density 650g/m^2 consisting of a yarn of 60% by mass co-mingled E-glass and carbon black pigmented polypropylene supplied by Vetrotex SA International under the trade name "Twintex™" was used throughout the studies. The glass fibres and the polypropylene filaments had nominal diameters of 17 and 20 - 25 microns respectively.

Specimens consisting solely of the glass reinforcement which is incorporated in Twintex were required in order to determine the compressive response of the fibre constituent. Samples of material were treated in a furnace at 400°C for 300 seconds to remove the polypropylene filaments without disturbing the glass fibre architecture.

Isothermal Compaction Trials

An Instron Universal Mechanical Testing Machine model 1195 with a 100 kN load cell and a model 3111 hot air oven was used to compact 100 x 100 mm squares of co-mingled fabric between steel platens. The temperature between the platens was monitored using K-type thermocouples. Four layers of fabric were placed into the platens at $180\text{-}185^\circ\text{C}$ with a thermocouple inserted into the centre of the fabric. When the temperature of the material reached 180°C the fabric was compacted at 1mm/min. The laminate was cooled to 100°C , the load removed and the plaque extracted.

To investigate the consolidation mechanism 4 samples were prepared, with compaction to 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% of the cross-head displacement required to produce full consolidation. The theoretical laminate height of 0.46mm/layer was calculated on the basis of the material superficial density, the constituent densities and fibre volume fraction. At 25% consolidation the reinforcement bundles were distinct and separate, with some matrix material interspersed within the bundle. At 50% consolidation the matrix had almost coalesced, but large voids remained within and around the bundles and dispersion of fibres within the matrix was uneven. At 75% consolidation the laminate still contained significant voidage, but matrix and reinforcement were well interspersed, and the longitudinal bundles were increasing in aspect ratio as they were compressed. At 100% consolidation, the fibre distribution had improved still further, and little voidage remained.

Sheared Fabric Compaction

In order to investigate the effect on the compaction response of in-plane fabric shear, 4 layers of Twintex fabric were sheared to the required angle in a parallelogram clamping frame. The fabric was then clamped at the periphery using a two-piece clamping frame, with one frame located below the fabric, and the other located above the fabric, the two halves being joined using captive bolts and wing nuts.

Three groups of sheared samples were compacted:

1. Fabric un-sheared, as a control.

2. Fabric sheared to the maximum shear angle attainable with this fabric, which was found to be approximately 25° at room temperature.
3. Fabric in a median state of shear, between zero and the determined maximum, which is approximately 13°.

The samples were sheared as described previously, and then compacted using an Instron model 1195 testing machine equipped with electrically heated platens. The platen temperature was regulated using one PID controller per platen, which was set to 190°C. The sheared fabric stack was placed into the platens with a K-type thermocouple inserted through the fabric into the stack centre. When the thermocouple within the material registered a temperature of 189°C, the material was compacted at 50mm/minute. Compaction was halted when the force at the load cell exceeded 45kN, or when the laminate was compacted to a height of 1.5mm.

Fig. 2: Pressure vs laminate height for compaction of sheared co-mingled fabric

Fig. 2 shows a plot of pressure vs laminate height for compaction of laminates which have been sheared by 0°, 12° and 22°. The theoretical minimum height for each laminate has been calculated on the basis that material is conserved when shear is applied, so that the height of a sheared sample may be calculated by Eqn. 1:

$$h_p = \frac{h_f}{\sin(90 - \theta)} \tag{1}$$

where h_f is the un-sheared minimum laminate height, θ is the angle of shear and h_{fs} is the minimum sheared laminate height. The theoretical minimum heights are marked on the graph as dashed lines. The curves show that the minimum height attained (all tests terminated at the upper load, rather than displacement, limit of 45kN = 3.4N/mm²) increases with increasing shear angle.

Figure 3 shows a plot of minimum laminate height vs. laminate shear angle. This also shows a trend of increasing laminate height with increasing shear angle, albeit with some scatter in the results. Again, the theoretical minimum height is plotted on this graph, and it should be

noted that all the experimental data lies above this curve. This may be attributed to incomplete consolidation of the test plaques - as soon as the upper load limit was reached during compaction, the testing machine cross-head returned to the upper set-point, removing all load from the plaque.

Fig. 3: Minimum Laminate Height Attained vs In-plane shear.

Consolidation Modelling

A 1-D isothermal consolidation model for co-mingled has been developed [8], which is based on the work of Van West [7] and uses the same single fibre bundle unit-cell, but differs from the original in several of the modelling assumptions which are applied. The model assumes a constant rate of compaction is applied to the material, the matrix material may be non-Newtonian, and the viscosity of the matrix material is temperature dependent. The material resistance to compaction is assumed to be the sum of the fibre bed compressive response and the matrix pressure. The impregnation portion of the model uses an 'effective bundle radius' which is determined as the distance the matrix must flow to wet out the fibres, and is based on observations of cross-sectional micrographs of the unconsolidated material. This model is composed of four sub-models:

Fibre Compaction

Modelling of the elastic response of the reinforcement is based on experimental data. Compaction tests were performed upon reinforcement only, which was obtained as described previously. The reinforcement was lubricated with an automotive 20/50 oil ("Century" supplied by Chemac Ltd), and a single layer of reinforcement was compacted at 1mm/minute using an Instron model 1195 testing machine. It was found that the behaviour of the fibre bed could be represented by a power-law relationship, where P_{fb} is the fibre bed pressure, h is the instantaneous fibre bed height, and h_0 is the initial fibre bed height, which was found to be 0.3mm:

$$P_{fb} = A \cdot \left(\frac{h}{h_0} \right)^b \quad (2)$$

The constants A and b were calculated to be 0.0355 and 10.0 respectively.

Permeability

A modified Kozeny-Carman equation as proposed by Gutowski [9] is used to predict the fibre bundle permeability coefficient:

$$K = \frac{r_i^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{v_a}{v_f}} - 1 \right)^3}{4k' \left(\frac{v_a}{v_f} + 1 \right)} \quad (3)$$

In Eqn (3), K is the permeability, r_i is the fibre radius and v_f is the instantaneous fibre volume fraction. The value of v_a , fibre volume fraction at zero permeability, was calculated to be 0.91 assuming hexagonal close packing of fibres. The value of k' , the modified Kozeny constant is based on Seo's work [10] and uses a value of 0.9.

Impregnation

Impregnation of the fibre bed is governed by Darcy's law, which can be applied to a compacting circular fibre bundle (Eqn 4). In this polar form, V_r is the fluid (matrix) velocity, U_r is the fibre velocity, P is the pressure, K is the permeability, and μ is the fluid viscosity. The subscript 'r' denotes 'at radius r'.

$$V_r - U_r = - \frac{K}{\mu} \cdot \frac{dp_r}{dr} \quad (4)$$

Matrix Shear Thinning

It is proposed that at ultimate compaction the reinforcing fibres will assume a hexagonal close packed structure, and at each intermediate stage of compaction the fibres will lie in a proportionately packed hexagonal array. The mean inter-fibre spacing x , can then be determined from the instantaneous volume fraction v_f by solving Eqn 5.

$$\left(\frac{x}{r_f} \right)^2 + 4 \left(\frac{x}{r_f} \right) + 4 = \frac{1}{\left(\cos \frac{\pi}{6} \cdot v_f \right)} \quad (5)$$

If the flow path between the fibres is idealised as a rectangular channel, then the shear-strain rate attributable to flow between the fibres is given by Eqn 6, where V is the matrix flow velocity, n is the matrix power-law index, and γ_a is the shear strain rate.

$$\gamma_a = \frac{2n + 1}{n} \left(\frac{2V}{x} \right) \quad (6)$$

The viscosity of the matrix is then determined from the manufacturer's power-law description of the matrix material shear/viscosity relationship at the required temperature using Eqn 7. For example, at 189° C, $B = 3971.9$ and $n = 0.37$.

$$\mu_a = B \cdot (\gamma_a)^{(n-1)} \quad (7)$$

Incorporation of In-plane Material Shear

The effect of in-plane material shear is incorporated into the consolidation model by modifying several geometrical parameters in order to conserve mass:

1. The initial, instantaneous and final laminate heights are increased using Eqn 1.
2. The *sheared* fabric fibre bundle aspect ratio A_r^* , is calculated from the undeformed fabric fibre bundle aspect ratio A_r using Eqn 8, where θ is the total deviation from 90° at the fibre cross-overs:

$$A_r^* = A_r \cdot \sin(90 - \theta) \quad (8)$$

The fibre bed sub-model is not explicitly modified, but the pressures predicted by this model will be increased with increasing material shear angles, because of the increase in fibre volume fraction at a given laminate height with increasing shear.

Fig 4 shows a plot of predicted developed moulding pressures at a laminate height of 2.625mm, and the corresponding experimental results. As expected, the predicted pressures increase with increasing shear angle, although this increase is greater than that displayed in the experimental results.

Figure 4: In-plane fabric shear vs developed moulding pressure, predicted and experimental results

HEAT TRANSFER

The cooling of a thin laminate may be idealised as a one-dimensional heat transfer problem. Internal heat conduction through the laminate thickness is governed by Eqn 9, where t is the time, T is the temperature, x is the through-thickness coordinate, and α is the thermal diffusivity of the laminate.

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

The laminate, which in the unconsolidated state consists of glass fibre, polypropylene and air, is idealised as a 'rule of mixtures' material [11]. That is, the laminate thermal properties are calculated on a proportionate basis using the thermal properties of the constituents.

Eqn 9 may be discretised using a forward finite difference scheme, giving an expression for the temperature at an interior node in the laminate in terms of the temperatures at the neighbouring nodes at the previous time step.

$$t_{n,t} = F \cdot (t_{(n-1),(t-\Delta t)} + t_{(n+1),(t-\Delta t)}) + t_{(n),(t-\Delta t)} \cdot (1 - 2F) \quad (10)$$

In Eqn 10, the first temperature subscript denotes the nodal position, and the second denotes the time step, while Δt is the time step and F is the fourier number.

This formulation has been used in a heat transfer model for laminate cooling. This model is intended to describe the through-thickness temperature distribution within the laminate from the end of the preheat stage until completion of the moulding cycle. Three distinct cooling regimes are imposed:

1. The material is removed from the preheat facility, and is transported to the press. Heat is lost by convection from the upper and lower laminate surfaces.
2. The material is placed in the mould, and the upper mould half is lowered towards the laminate. Heat is lost by convection from the upper surface, and conduction from the lower surface.
3. The mould is closed, and compression of the laminate begins. Heat is lost by conduction from both upper and lower laminate surfaces until the moulding cycle is completed.

Fig. 6 shows sample output for the process heat transfer model for laminate materials, for a nominal thermoforming process which uses a preheat temperature of 200° C, with a transit time from preheat to first tool contact of 10 seconds and a tool closure time of 3 seconds. The tools are assumed to be massive in relation to the laminate charge and so maintain a steady-state temperature of 20°C. This figure shows that the heat lost during transport is relatively insignificant when compared to the much more rapid heat loss via conduction, which occurs once the material is placed in the mould.

Fig: 6: Laminate process heat transfer model, sample output

PROCESS MODEL INTEGRATION

The simplest basis for integration of the three process models is based on the assumption that during the moulding of a component comprised from a co-mingled thermoplastic composite, deformation and consolidation of the fabric occur consecutively: The material is introduced into the mould cavity and is formed during mould closure. Consolidation commences once forming is complete. Laminate cooling may be modelled from the end of the preheat cycle until all points within the laminate fall below the crystallisation temperature of the matrix material.

This idealisation allows the moulding process to be modelled by using the fabric deformation model to determine the local fibre orientations within the mould. If in-plane matrix flow is prohibited, then simulation of the compaction of the draped form is reduced to a serial application for the consolidation model to each area of the deformed fabric on a facet-by-facet basis.

Fig. 6 shows the predicted fibre orientations when a fabric is formed over a 100mm diameter hemisphere. The main captions denote the fibre crossover angles, which have been used in conjunction with the consolidation model for sheared co-mingled materials to estimate the developed moulding pressures for in-mould compaction of this part at 50mm/minute. The pressure estimates are given as the bracketed values directly below the relevant material shear angle.

The heat transfer from the fabric can be considered during both deformation and consolidation by dividing the fabric thickness into a number of sub-layers. Using the through-thickness temperature distribution which is given by the heat transfer model, the material state may be determined within each sub-layer. The known temperatures can be used to determine the state of the matrix within each sub-layer, and if molten, the viscosity of the matrix can be ascertained. This updated viscosity data can be supplied to the consolidation model, allowing the effect of local cooling as well as local fibre-architecture deformation to be accounted for.

Fig. 6: Draped hemisphere, showing fibre orientations and consolidation pressure estimates

CONCLUSIONS

The three principal processes which control the moulding of a co-mingled thermoplastic composite have been identified, and a process model for each has been developed. Partial integration of the deformation and consolidation models has been achieved, and a strategy for complete integration of the process models has been proposed.

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